

TABLE 3

Constituents in Bauxite solution	Optical densities of the eluted solutions after separation by Paper Electrophoresis	Concentrations of the eluted solutions calculated from the different calibration curves	Percentage of the constituents calculated from molar concentrations, volume of migrants, volume of diluents and weight of Bauxite taken	Actual percentage of the constituents calculated by standard methodical analysis
Al ₂ O ₃	0.026	6.9×10^{-6} Molar	53.8%	53.8%
TiO ₂	0.02	0.24×10^{-4} Molar	11%	11.82%
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.03	0.3×10^{-5} Molar	2.575%	2.5%

ferric ammonium sulphate (standardised by standard potassium dichromate) for iron were prepared. By taking different aliquot portions of these solutions calibration curve for aluminium, titanium and iron were drawn from the data as shown in the Table 2.

From the calibration curves of aluminium, titanium and iron the molar concentration of these eluted solutions were calculated and the percentages of Al₂O₃, TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ in bauxite were calculated as given in the Table 3.

From the table 3, it shows that the technique can be equally utilised for the separation and estimation of aluminium, titanium and iron in bauxite.

Moreover, even with a micro amount of bauxite solution (4.32×10^{-5} gm in 0.01 ml of solution) and within few hours the estimation of the major constituents that is, iron, aluminium and titanium can be done easily without interference when usual standard methods are time consuming, laborious and special cares are to be taken to avoid interference.

References

- (a) WILFRED W. SCOTT, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis" (Fifth Edition), D. Van Nostrand Company Inc., p. 23.
- (b) JULIUS GRANT, "Clowes and Coleman's Quantitative Chemical Analysis" (15th Edition), J. & A. Churchill Ltd., London, p. 293.
- (c) J. J. PUERTOLAS, *Ions*, 1945, 5, 277.
- (d) H. A. LIEBHAFSKY, H. G. PHEIFFER, E. H. WINSLOW and P. D. ZEMANY, "X-rays, Electrons and Analytical Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1972, pp. 536, 537, 539.
- (e) WALTER WAGNER, CLARENCE J. HULL and E. MARKLE, "Advanced Analytical Chemistry", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, pp. 148, 171, 249.
2. H. G. MUKHERJEE and S. P. NAG, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, 33, 197.
3. E. L. DURRUM, R. J. BLOCK and G. ZWIG, *A Manual of Paper Chromatography and Paper Electrophoresis*, Academic Press Inc. Publishers, New York, 1955, p. 351. fig. 4.
4. G. CHARLOT and DENISE BEZIER, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Methuen & Co. Ltd., London, pp. 609, 329.

Magneto-Paper Electrophoresis in the Study of Inorganic Ions. Part. II*

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THE paper describes a comparative study of magnetophoresis, electrophoresis and magneto-electrophoresis with reference to paramagnetic inorganic ions, specially the lanthanide ions. A binodal curve similar to that obtained by plotting μ_{eff} (effective magnetic moments) of the lanthanide (+3) ions at 300°K against atomic number of lanthanons, supports the possible separation of lanthanons by magneto-paper electrophoresis method.

Comparative study :

Successful separation of various inorganic ions by magneto-paper electrophoresis² prompted us to undertake a comparative study of allied techniques¹.

Experimental

An apparatus² with minor modification in order to avoid the hydrostatic flow of the electrolyte, of the following type (Fig. 1) is used.

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig. 1.

In case of magnetophoresis the key K₁ is disconnected, so that there is no electric-field, whereas in case of electrophoresis the key K₂ is taken out

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when there is no magnetic-field in the circuit. Only in case of magneto-electrophoresis both the keys K_1, K_2 are connected to have both the electric- and the magnetic-field simultaneously in the circuit.

Whatman No. 1 filter paper is cut into strips of 1 cm x 35 cm. One drop of the aqueous solution of the ions, concentration being 0.5 mg/ml is placed on the central region of the paper previously marked with a lead-pencil. The paper is now moistened carefully with 0.1 M KCl and sandwiched between the glass-plates. This is then passed through the pole pieces of the electro-magnet and the paper ends are dipped into the carrier electrolyte. Then the necessary field is applied by connecting K_1 and/or K_2 keys. Both the potential difference and the strength of magnetic-field are kept steady by adjusting the rheostat R_h and resistance R. Individual ions are subjected to magnetophoresis, electrophoresis and magneto-electrophoresis successively for 25 minutes using 0.1M KCl as carrier electrolyte. After the experiment, the paper is air dried and then the migrants are located by spraying with proper developing agent.

TABLE 1

Ion	Magnetic moment ^a	Position of the central line of the band from the origin in mm			Developing agent
		Magneto-phoresis	Electro-phoresis	Magneto-Electro-phoresis	
Cu ²⁺	1.8-2.2	3	17	15	Rubeanic Acid
Ni ²⁺	2.9-3.4	3.5	25	22	"
Co ²⁺	4.4-5.2	2	28	26	"
Fe ²⁺	5.0-5.5	2.5	35	32	$K_3Fe(CN)_6$
Mn ²⁺	5.2-6.0	2	31.5	25	NaOH
Cd ²⁺	0	2.5	18	18.5	$(NH_4)_2S_x$
$Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$	2.3	6	36	31	Fe^{2+}
$Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$	0	7.5	40	41	Fe^{3+}

p.d. : 160 volts ; Magnetic-field : 15 kilogauss ; Current : 1.5 amp.

From the result of the table 1, it appears that the magneto-paper-electrophoresis is a better tool in the study and separation of ions specially of paramagnetic ions. This new technique has been successfully applied for :

(a) Separation of paramagnetic ions from diamagnetic ones, e.g. ferricyanide has been separated from ferrocyanide in 20 minutes using 0.1M HCl as background electrolyte. Band position in mm : $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ 16 to 22 and $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ 30 to 35 towards anode. (b) Separation of high-spin complexes from low spin complexes of the same metal ions in the same valence state, e.g. ferrifluoride from ferricyanide in 20 minutes using 0.1M KCl as carrier electrolyte. Band position in mm : FeF_6^{3-} 8 to 14 and $Fe(CN)_6^{3-}$ 18 to 22 towards anode. (c) Separation of lanthanid ions of different paramagnetism, e.g. La(III) from Gd(III) in 30 minutes using 0.05 citric acid as background electro lyte. Band position in mm : La^{3+} 0 to 5 and Gd^{3+} 12 to 16 towards cathode.

Study of Lanthanons :

The trivalent rare-earth nitrates are subjected to paper-electrophoresis for 30 minutes using 0.1M KNO_3 as background electrolyte. The same experiments are repeated in the magnetic-field. The difference in electromigration of the individual ions with (d_1) and without (d_2) magnetic-field are appreciable. The ratio $(d_2 - d_1)/d_2$ for each lanthanide (+3) ion is also included in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Lanthanide Ions (+3)	Electromigration distance of the central line of the band from origin in mm		$\frac{d_2 - d_1}{d_2}$
	In magnetic field (d_1)	Without magnetic field (d_2)	
La	22	24	.08
Ce	17	22	.23
Pr	15	23	.35
Nd	13	23	.43
Sm	17	23	.26
Eu	14	23	.39
Gd	6.5	23	.72
Tb	5.5	22	.75
Dy	5	24	.80
Ho	4.5	22.5	.80
Er	9.5	22	.57
Yb	13	24	.46
Lu	23	25	.08

p.d. : 160 volts ; Magnetic-field : 15 kilogauss ; Current : 1.5 amp.

The ratio $(d_2 - d_1)/d_2$ when plotted against the atomic number of the individual lanthanides, gives a curve³, similar to that obtained by plotting μ_{eff} (effective magnetic moment) of the lanthanide (+3) ions at 300°K against the atomic number of the lanthanides (Fig. 2).

Discussion

The application of an external magnetic-field with the electrophoresis influences the migration of the paramagnetic ions, which is retarded with increasing paramagnetism.

The possibility of the separation of the $Fe^{3+} - Cu^{2+}, Ni(NH_3)_4^{2+} - Co(NH_3)_6^{3+}, Fe(CN)_6^{3-} - Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, etc. are thus due to the differences in their magnetic moments. Larger the strength of the magnetic-field, larger is the extent of diminution of migration of the particular paramagnetic ion. It is also evident that the separation of the paramagnetic

ions may even be possible by passing the zone chromatographically through the magnetic-field only, if the strength of the magnetic-field is considerably high ($\gg 15$ kilogauss).

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References

- H. KUNKEL and A. TISELIUS, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1951, **35**, 89;
A. K. MAJUMDER and H. G. MUKHERJEE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **15**, 547;
T. WIELAND and E. FISCHER, *Naturwiss.*, 1948, **35**, 29;
R. P. SHUKLA and L. M. LALL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 283.
- H. G. MUKHERJEE and D. MAJUMDER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **277**, 205.
- P. W. SELWOOD, *Magneto-Chemistry*, 2nd Ed. 1956, 159.
F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, 1969, 1058.

Potentiometric Study of $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ Salicylaldehyde System

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URANYL chelates with phenolic compounds and carboxylic acids have been studied extensively^{1,6}.

In the present study the interactions of uranyl ion with salicylaldehyde in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture at 30° and 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength have been investigated by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The effect of ionic strength on proton (pK) and metal ligand stability constant ($\log K$) is observed by examining the system at $\mu=0.029$ M, 0.049 M, 0.069 M, 0.089 M and 0.109 M. The influence of the solvent is studied by evaluating pK and $\log K$ values in 10%, 25%, 40%, 60% and 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures.

All the reagents used were of AR quality. The method of purification of dioxane, the procedure employed and the methods used for the calculations of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} , pK and $\log K$ are the same as given earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

pK and $\log K_1$ values (Table 1) decrease with an increase of ionic strength. The data were analysed by the Bronsted equation

$$\log K = \log K^\circ + A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}$$

The plots of pK and $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ were linear.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF URANYL CHELATES WITH SALICYLALDEHYDE

μ	pK	μ	$\log K_1$
0.029	12.69	0.031	12.01
0.049	12.54	0.071	11.71
0.069	12.46	0.110	11.43
0.089	12.37		
0.109	12.31		

Accuracy 0.02 to 0.05.

Knowing $A=6.78^8$ the magnitude of ΔZ^2 was calculated which is given below :

Reaction	ΔZ^2 values	
	obs.	calc.
$\text{HL} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{L}^-$	-2.26	2
$\text{UO}_2^{2+} + \text{HL} \rightleftharpoons \text{UO}_2\text{L}^+ + \text{H}^+$	-2.07	2

By making use of modified Bronsted-Christian

equation⁹ $\log K = \log K^\circ + \frac{A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + Ba \sqrt{\mu}}$ in which size

of ions were obtained by trial method [$a=7\text{\AA}$ for salicylaldehyde, and $a=6\text{\AA}$ for $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ salicylaldehyde], the observed linearity between pK

vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{5.39\sqrt{\mu}}$ and $\log K$, vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+4.62\sqrt{\mu}}$ for both

systems respectively was much better than given by earlier plots. The plots gave value of $A\Delta Z^2$ for salicylaldehyde and for $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ -salicylaldehyde as 13.54 and 13.11 respectively which did not show any appreciable improvement over the previous values.

The values of thermodynamic constants obtained from the plots of $pK/\log K$ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+Ba\sqrt{\mu}}$ are in agreement with the theoretical values. These values are as follows :

Salicylaldehyde	$pK^\circ = 13.90$
$\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ -Salicylaldehyde	$\log K_1^\circ = 13.25$

Effect of the dielectric constant of the medium :

For the purpose of investigating the effect of dielectric constant on the complexation reaction, the two systems were studied in 10%, 25%, 60% and 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures. The values of pK , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ increase with an increase in the percentage of dioxane (Table 2). The plots of

$pK/\log K_1$ vs $\frac{1}{D}$ and plots of pK and $\log K_1$ vs mole fraction are found to be linear.